

Fluoroborates : Part II. Trihydroxymonofluoroborates

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The preparation and properties of the salts of the series, $M^I\text{BF}(\text{OH})_3$, where $M = \text{K, Rb, Cs}$ and $\frac{2}{3}\text{Ni}$, have been prepared by reacting boric acid with the corresponding metallic fluoride. The conductometric and thermometric titrations of $\text{KBF}(\text{OH})_3$ by HF show the successive formation of $\text{BF}_2(\text{OH})_2^-$, BF_3OH^- and BF_4^- ions. Through conductance and ion-exchange studies the trihydroxymonofluoroborate ion has been found to dissociate considerably into fluoride ion and boric acid. The X-ray and infra-red spectra of the potassium salt have been given, and compared with those of boric acid, potassium tetrafluoro- and monohydroxytrifluoroborates. Potassium trihydroxymonofluoroborate has been found to yield mix-crystals and overgrowths with the corresponding permanganate and perchlorate, thus showing the isomorphism between the three compounds.

Various fluoboric acids and salts derived from them have been described in the literature¹. Of these the tetra-fluoboric acid and its salts have been well characterised and studied thoroughly. A number of hydroxyfluoboric acids may be presumed to result by hydrolysis through substitution of the fluoride atom by hydroxyl group. The corresponding acids may be written as follows : HBF_4 , $\text{HBF}_3(\text{OH})$, $\text{HBF}_2(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{HBF}(\text{OH})_3$. Of the above possible hydrofluoboric acids the monohydroxy- and the dihydroxy- acids have been reported^{3,4,5} whilst the trihydroxy acid has remained unknown.

In our previous communication² we have shown from conductometric, thermometric and phase rule studies the existence of $\text{BF}(\text{OH})_3^-$ ion in aqueous solution. The present work deals with the isolation of the trihydroxyfluoroborates and study of their properties.

The isomorphism of the tetrafluoroborates with the perchlorates and permanganates is well established^{6,7,8}. The following ionic radii values^{9,10} suggest that the probable hydroxy-

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fluoborate ions being isoelectronic should be isomorphous with one another, and also should be isomorphous with the tetrafluoborate, perchlorate and permanganate.

Ionic radius, A		Tonic radius, A	
B ⁺³	0.20	O ²⁻	1.40
Cl ⁺⁷	0.26	OH ⁻	1.40
Mn ⁺⁷	0.46	F ⁻	1.36

Meerwein and Pannewitz¹¹ claimed to have isolated the sodium and potassium monohydroxytrifluoborates by reaction of an ethereal suspension of caustic alkali with (C₂H₅)₂O. BF₃. The study of crystal structure of the sodium salt thus prepared showed it to be isomorphous with the corresponding fluoborate⁸. But Ryss and others¹² have shown that the sodium salt used in the above study was probably not a monohydroxytrifluoborate, but a mixture of NaBF₄, NaF, NaBO₂ and NaOH.

In the present study we have examined the case of isomorphism of the potassium trihydroxymonofluoborate (briefly reported earlier¹³) with the corresponding perchlorate and permanganate.

Travers and Malaprade¹⁴ reported that cold concentrated aqueous solutions of boric acid and potassium fluoride react to yield crystals containing boron and potassium in a one-to-one ratio, and fluorine and boron in a three-to-one ratio. Contrary to their observations the present authors have found that reaction of boric acid and potassium fluoride produce well-defined crystals of potassium trihydroxymonofluoborate only and no other fluoborate.

EXPERIMENTAL

The chemicals used in the present work were of reagent grade quality.

The alkali metals were estimated as their corresponding sulphates after fuming the compounds with concentrated sulphuric acid and methyl alcohol. In a similar manner nickel was estimated as its dimethylglyoxime compound by standard procedures.

For the estimation of boron in the alkali metal compounds the substances were fused with sodium hydroxide, extracted with water, excess calcium chloride solution added and boiled. The solution was then just acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid against methyl red and refluxed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. After cooling Wesselow's indicator [methyl red (0.25% in alcohol) + methylene blue (0.16% in alcohol) in 1 : 1 ratio] added and the excess acid was just neutralised with dilute sodium hydroxide. Excess mannitol (2-3 gms) was added and the solution titrated by standard sodium hydroxide against phenolphthalein till pink colour persisted. Boron was estimated in the nickel compound by following the above procedure but after filtering off the nickel oxide produced during the fusion.

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Fluorine was estimated as calcium fluoride by following standard procedures after decomposing the substances by fusion with sodium carbonate. Fluorine in the nickel compound was determined from the filtrate obtained by fusing the substance with sodium carbonate and filtering.

For the conductometric titrations individual mixtures for each point were prepared in polythene bottles keeping the total volume constant. Blank solutions were also prepared in a similar manner. The solutions were allowed to stand for two weeks, and the conductances were measured with dip type platinised platinum electrodes fitted into polythene tubes and using a polythene container. The conductances were recorded with a Philips Conductivity measuring apparatus, Type PR-9500. The results of conductometric titration of $\text{KBF}(\text{OH})_3$ by HF were plotted in Fig. 1. The measurement of conductance of potassium

Fig. 1. Curve I. 10 ml. $\text{KBF}(\text{OH})_3$ solution (0.1391 M) was titrated conductometrically by HF (0.1131 M) at constant volume (60 ml.).

Curve II. 10 ml. $\text{KBF}(\text{OH})_3$ solution (0.1458 M) titrated by HF (0.1174 M).

trihydroxymonofluoborate solutions at different dilutions were made immediately and after twelve days, but no difference was noticed. The data were represented in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Conductance of Potassium trihydroxymonofluoborate solutions at different dilutions

V (dilution)	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024
λ_v	109.6	121.7	121.8	127.1	134.9	135.9	144.6
λ_∞	128.5	136.7	132.2	134.8	140.6	140.1	147.7

The λ_∞ values were calculated from Walden's formula, $\lambda_\infty = \lambda_\infty (1 + n_1 n_2 \times 0.692 \times v^{-1})$, where v = dilution, n_1 and n_2 are the valencies of the ions.

The thermometric titrations of $\text{KBF}(\text{OH})_3$ by HF were carried out by following usual procedures and taking the necessary precautions^{1,15}. Blank titrations of water by

hydrofluoric acid were also made. The data were represented in Fig. 2 after making the necessary volume correction and subtracting the blank values.

Ion-exchange experiments were made with a column filled with ion-exchange resin, Dowex 21K, chloride form.

Potassium tetrafluoroborate¹⁶ and potassium monohydroxy trifluoroborate¹⁷ were prepared according to standard procedures.

Fig. 2. Curve I. 60 ml. $\text{KBF}(\text{OH})_3$ solution (0.08275 M) was titrated thermometrically by HF (0.7098 M). Curve II. 60 ml. $\text{KBF}(\text{OH})_3$ solution (0.06898 M) was titrated by HF (0.7098 M).

1. *Potassium trihydroxymonofluoroborate, $\text{KBF}(\text{OH})_3$* : To a saturated solution (20 ml) of potassium fluoride (18.5 g) contained in a polythene beaker boric acid (9.8 g) was added in fractions with constant stirring. The resulting clear mixture was kept in a polythene basin inside a desiccator. When the crystals began to appear after 2–3 days, the solution was stirred with a polythene rod, a large number of rhombohedral crystals then appeared evolving considerable amount of heat. The crystals were then filtered off by suction, washed successively with ice-cold water and alcohol (1 : 1), dried in air and analysed. (Found, K, 33.33; B, 8.85; F, 15.03%; $\text{KBF}(\text{OH})_3$ requires K, 32.61; B, 9.02, F, 15.85%). The substance can be recrystallised from water (Analytical data of recrystallised sample K, 32.58; B, 8.90; F, 15.70%). The compound can be salted out from the aqueous solution by adding an excess of potassium acetate and washing out the latter by alcohol during filtration. The substance was found not to be hygroscopic and its solubility was determined to be 32.9 g per 100 ml of water at 31°. Its melting point (uncorrected) has been registered to be 88°.

2. *Rubidium trihydroxymonofluoroborate, $\text{RbBF}(\text{OH})_3$* : Boric acid (5 g) was added to an aqueous solution (30 ml.) of rubidium fluoride, which was prepared by reacting rubidium chloride (10 g) with stoichiometric amount of freshly prepared silver fluoride and

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filtering off the precipitated silver chloride. The resulting mixture was then evaporated in a desiccator till white crystals appeared from the viscous liquid. The crystals were washed with alcohol (1 : 1), dried in a desiccator and analysed. (Found : Rb, 51.45; B, 6.37; F, 11.08%); $\text{RbBF}(\text{OH})_3$ required Rb, 51.40; B, 6.50; F, 11.42%. The crystals were hygroscopic and highly soluble in water. It melts at 270° (with decomposition).

3. *Cesium trihydroxymonofluoborate, $\text{CsBF}(\text{OH})_3$* : By reacting cesium fluoride and boric acid the cesium salt was prepared in an analogous manner as the rubidium salt. It was obtained as a pasty mass in vacuum over phosphorus pentoxide. (Found : Cs, 62.24; B, 4.94; F, 8.5%; $\text{CsBF}(\text{OH})_3$ requires : Cs, 62.18; B, 5.06; F, 8.89%).

4. *Nickel trihydroxymonofluoborate, $\text{Ni}[\text{BF}(\text{OH})_3]_2 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$* : The nickel salt was isolated as green hygroscopic crystals by reacting solutions of nickel perchlorate with stoichiometric quantity of potassium trihydroxymonofluoborate, filtering off the precipitated potassium perchlorate, and evaporating the filtrate in a desiccator. (Found : Ni, 18.69; B, 7.06; F, 11.90%; $\text{Ni}[\text{BF}(\text{OH})_3]_2 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, requires : Ni, 18.92; B, 6.97; F, 12.20%).

In the case of NH_4^+ , Na^+ , $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NH}^+$, $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}^+$ and Tl^+ ions no pure compound could be isolated by metathetical reactions of respective metallic perchlorates and potassium trihydroxymonofluoborate solutions or from a reaction of metallic fluorides and boric acid. With cations *e.g.*, Zn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+}$ etc., salts of this series also could not be isolated due to the separation of respective metallic fluorides, when metathetical reactions of their perchlorates and potassium trihydroxymonofluoborate were attempted.

The $\text{BF}(\text{OH})_3^-$ ion is stable in solutions having *pH* ranges between 4.5 and 8.5. This was suggested by the decomposition of the ion during attempts to recrystallise $\text{KBF}(\text{OH})_3$ from acetic acid or potassium hydroxide solutions.

Mix-crystal study with KMnO_4 : Potassium trihydroxymonofluoborate was found to yield mix-crystals with potassium permanganate, when a pinch of the latter was allowed to dissolve in a saturated solution of the fluoborate and then crystallised by constant stirring in the cold condition. The pinkish white crystals were washed with ice-cold water and filter pressed, dried in air and analysed. Found : K, 32.73; B, 8.72; Mn, 0.36 and F, 14.24%. These data showed $\text{K} : (\text{B} + \text{Mn}) : \text{F} = 1.04 : 1 : 0.93$.

Overgrowth Study: A minute crystal of potassium perchlorate was placed in a saturated solution of potassium monohydroxytrifluoborate in a polythene container. After 2–3 months a big crystal with the perchlorate nucleus inside was obtained. It was washed with water, dried and analysed. Found : K, 32.40; B, 8.71; F, 14.97 and Cl, 0.33%. These data showed $\text{K} : (\text{B} + \text{Cl}) : \text{F} = 0.99 : 1 : 0.94$.

X-ray study: The X-ray powder diffraction spectra (Table 2) of $\text{KBF}(\text{OH})_3$ was taken along with the spectra of KBF_4 , $\text{KBF}_3(\text{OH})$ and H_3BO_3 using a Guinier camera with $\text{Cu}-\text{K}_\alpha$ radiation.

Infra-red study: The infra-red spectra of KBF_4 , $\text{KBF}_3(\text{OH})$, $\text{KBF}(\text{OH})_3$ and H_3BO_3 have been recorded with a Perkin-Elmer apparatus. The data for the trihydroxyfluoborate are : 690 (S), 790 (S), 890–930 (B), 1070–1170 (B), 1425 (S), 3200 (S) cm^{-1} , where S = sharp and B = broad absorption bands.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The present authors have isolated salts of M^I $[BF(OH)_3]$ series, where $M^I = K, Rb, Cs$ and $\frac{1}{2}Ni$. The conductometric and thermometric titrations of potassium trihydroxy-monofluoborate by HF (Figs. 1 and 2) showed breaks at the $KBF(OH)_3 : HF$ ratios of 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3. These inflection points therefore correspond to the formation of $BF_2(OH)^-$, $BF_3(OH)^-$ and BF_4^- ions.

TABLE 2

X-ray powder diffraction spectra of KBF_3OH and $KBF(OH)_3$ using $Cu-K_\alpha$ radiation.

KBF ₃ OH		KBF(OH) ₃	
Relative Intensity	dÅ	Relative Intensity	dÅ
VW	6.21	W	5.40
VW	5.86	W	5.26
VW	4.11	W	4.83
VW	3.84	VW	4.13
VW	3.69	M	3.97
M	3.56	W	3.78
W	3.44	M	3.48
S	3.26	S	2.96
S	3.24	VW	2.95
M	3.11	VS	2.91
M	3.09	VS	2.81
M	2.99	VW	2.72
W	2.93	VW	2.62
M	2.85	M	2.56
M	2.81	M	2.46
VW	2.74	VW	2.41
VW	2.57	VW	2.37
W	2.46	W	2.27
W	2.44	S	2.25
W	2.41	M	2.14
M	2.31	M	2.10
M	2.28	M	2.09
W	2.24	VW	2.05
W	2.22	W	2.01
M	2.20	M	1.96
M	2.19	VW	1.82
W	2.15		
W	2.10	VW	1.81
VW	2.08	M	1.74
VW	2.06	VW	1.73
M	2.03	M	1.71
W	2.01		

VS = very strong; S = strong; M = medium; W = weak; VW = very weak.

The X-ray (Table 2) and infra-red spectra of the potassium salt showed it to be a pure compound free from boric acid. The valency of the anion, $BF(OH)_3$, has been calculated

to be one (viz. 0.98, 1.009) applying Walden's formula and using the λ_v values (vide Table 1) at 256 and 512 dilutions where λ_∞ values have been found to be almost the same. The λ_∞ values, however, point to the progressive dissociation of the complex ion with dilution.

By passing a solution of potassium trihydroxymonofluoborate (1%) through anion exchanger, chloride form, and washing with water, it has been found that the whole amount of fluoride was retained in the column whilst the total quantity of boric acid generated by dissociation passed through. The above studies, therefore, suggested a strong dissociation of the complex ion according to the following equation,

The potassium salt of BF(OH)_3^- series has been found to yield mix-crystals with potassium permanganate (vide supra). The salt also produced overgrowth on a potassium perchlorate crystal (vide supra). These observations, therefore, suggested that the BF(OH)_3^- ion was isomorphous with MnO_4^- and ClO_4^- ions. From the X-ray spectra of KBF_4 , (well-known), $\text{KBF}_3(\text{OH})$ and KBF(OH)_3 (Table 2) it has been found that the three compounds were not isomorphous with one another. It may be mentioned here that the X-ray diffraction spectra of $\text{KBF}_3(\text{OH})$ have not been reported before.

The IR-spectra of potassium trihydroxymonofluoborate (vide supra) show the presence of typical sharp absorption bands^{18,19,20} corresponding to B-F and B-OH found in KBF_4 and $\text{KBF}_3(\text{OH})$ and also due to B-O at 1425 cm^{-1} . It is interesting to note that the spectra of KBF(OH)_3 and $\text{KBF}_3(\text{OH})$ are somewhat different from one another. This is, probably, due to the different environmental conditions around the central boron atoms in the two compounds.

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